

Impact of International Financial Reporting Standards Adoption on Financial Reporting Quality in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) adoption on financial reporting quality in Nigerian quoted manufacturing companies, focusing on variations across time (2020–2024) and firm size categories. Adopting a descriptive survey research design with a quantitative approach, a purposive sample of ten manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) was selected based on full IFRS compliance and availability of complete audited financial statements from 2020 to 2024. Secondary data from annual reports were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), with Return on Assets (ROA) as a proxy for financial reporting quality. The results reveal no statistically significant differences in mean ROA across the years 2020–2024 ($F(4,26) = 0.5854, p = 0.8043$), indicating that IFRS adoption did not produce measurable year-to-year improvements in reporting quality during the review period. However, significant differences were found across firm size categories ($F(2,27) = 13.1752, p < 0.001$), with large firms demonstrating substantially higher mean ROA (0.1378) compared to medium (0.0485) and small (0.0212) firms, suggesting that larger firms benefit more from IFRS adoption due to superior resources and technical capacity. The findings imply that IFRS adoption alone is insufficient to guarantee improved financial reporting quality in developing economies like Nigeria; regulators must strengthen enforcement mechanisms and provide targeted capacity-building initiatives for smaller firms, while audit firms and corporate boards should prioritize governance structures that support rigorous IFRS implementation. This study contributes to the limited empirical literature on post-IFRS adoption outcomes in Nigerian manufacturing firms by highlighting the moderating role of firm size, offering critical insights for policymakers seeking to bridge the compliance gap between large and small firms in emerging markets.

Keywords: Financial reporting quality, Firm size, International financial reporting standards, Return on assets, Nigeria, Manufacturing companies

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Introduction

In recent years, globalization has significantly influenced accounting and financial reporting across the globe. In response, the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) introduced the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) to ensure that financial statements are comparable, reliable, transparent, and understandable across international boundaries. IFRS has become a benchmark for global financial reporting, replacing numerous national standards that were once varied and sometimes inconsistent (Abata & Adejuwon, 2020).

Nigeria, like many developing nations, recognized the need to align its financial reporting framework with global best practices. In 2010, the Federal Executive Council approved the roadmap for the adoption of IFRS, and by 2012, public entities were mandated to prepare their financial statements in accordance with IFRS. This transition was expected to increase investor confidence, improve transparency, attract foreign investment, and enhance comparability of financial statements.

Before IFRS, financial statements in Nigeria were prepared using the Statements of Accounting Standards (SAS) issued by the Nigerian Accounting Standards Board (NASB). However, SAS lacked the depth and global acceptance needed in the current financial environment. The move to SSIFRS, though welcomed by many, has been met with mixed results. While some claim that IFRS adoption has significantly improved the quality of financial reporting, others argue that the lack of full implementation, poor enforcement mechanisms, and inadequate training have limited its effectiveness.

Financial reporting quality is crucial for economic development as it influences decisions by investors, lenders, regulators, and other stakeholders. It is evaluated based on qualitative attributes such as relevance, faithful representation, comparability, verifiability, timeliness, and understandability (Tiamiyu, & Oyedokun, 2019; Adegbite & Rahman, 2021). IFRS was designed to enhance these attributes. Therefore, this study is timely in assessing whether the adoption of IFRS in Nigeria has truly translated into improved financial reporting quality.

This research is particularly important given that Nigeria is a developing economy with peculiar challenges such as weak regulatory systems, low corporate governance standards, and limited financial literacy. Understanding whether IFRS adoption has overcome these challenges to deliver improved reporting quality is vital to policy formulation, investor protection, and economic sustainability. The main objective of this study is to assess the impact of IFRS adoption on financial reporting quality in Nigeria.

Specific objectives are set to:

- i. examine the level of compliance with IFRS among Nigerian firms.
- ii. evaluate the changes in the qualitative characteristics of financial reports before and after IFRS adoption.

Literature Review

International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS)

International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) are a globally recognized set of accounting rules and principles developed by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB). These standards aim to bring uniformity, transparency, and comparability to the financial statements of organizations across different countries (Adegbite & Rahman, 2021). IFRS are principle-based standards that prioritize the economic substance of transactions over their legal form,

thereby providing a more accurate reflection of a company's financial performance and position.

IFRS was introduced as a response to the growing complexity of financial markets and the increasing need for a common language in financial reporting. The core objectives of IFRS include improving the quality of financial reporting, facilitating cross-border investments, enhancing investor confidence, and supporting global economic integration (Adegbite & Rahman, 2021). These standards are continuously reviewed and updated to reflect changing business environments and emerging financial reporting needs.

In Nigeria, the adoption of IFRS began in 2012 with publicly listed companies, followed by phased adoption for other categories of entities. This decision was based on Nigeria's need to align its financial reporting with international best practices, improve the quality of its capital markets, attract foreign investment, and ensure better accountability and transparency in financial reporting (Adetula & Owolabi, 2019; Ogundajo, Odunayo, Osunsusi, Desi, & Oyedokun, 2023). The Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) is the primary regulatory body responsible for overseeing IFRS compliance and implementation.

While IFRS adoption in Nigeria is a commendable step towards modernization, it is not without challenges. The implementation process has been met with resistance from some firms due to high costs of compliance, the complexity of the standards, limited availability of trained personnel, and gaps in institutional enforcement. Nonetheless, IFRS remains a critical tool for elevating the quality of corporate financial disclosures in Nigeria.

Financial Reporting Quality

Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ) refers to the extent to which financial statements faithfully and accurately depict an entity's economic performance and position, enabling users to make informed economic decisions (Ahmed & Fawehinmi, 2022). High-quality financial reports are those that present information that is relevant, faithfully represented, comparable, verifiable, timely, and understandable.

The IASB's conceptual framework identifies two fundamental qualitative characteristics of useful financial information: relevance and faithful representation. Relevance means that the information provided can influence users' economic decisions by helping them evaluate past, present, or future events (Oyedokun, Okwuosa, & Isah, 2019; Ahmed & Fawehinmi, 2022). It encompasses predictive and confirmatory values. Faithful representation implies that the information is complete, neutral, and free from error, thus reflecting the true economic substance of transactions.

Enhancing characteristics such as comparability, verifiability, timeliness, and understandability further support the usefulness of financial information. Comparability enables users to assess similarities and differences across entities and reporting periods. Verifiability provides assurance that different observers would arrive at similar conclusions

based on the same data. Timeliness ensures that information is available when it is needed for decision-making, and understandability ensures that users can comprehend the information without undue effort.

Financial reporting quality is critical to efficient capital market operations. It helps reduce information asymmetry between company management and external users such as investors, creditors, and regulators (Ojo, Oyedokun, & Fodio, 2020; Ali & Hassan, 2021). It also minimizes the risk of misreporting, enhances market confidence, and supports better resource allocation. Poor-quality financial reporting, on the other hand, can mislead users, impair investment decisions, and undermine the credibility of capital markets.

IFRS and Financial Reporting Quality

The adoption of IFRS is believed to significantly influence the quality of financial reporting. This belief is based on IFRS's comprehensive disclosure requirements, emphasis on fair value accounting, and focus on principles rather than rigid rules (Ali & Hassan, 2021; Oyedokun, Abdullahi & Oyedokun, 2025). These attributes are expected to enhance the transparency, accuracy, and comparability of financial statements.

Before the adoption of IFRS, Nigerian firms relied on the Nigerian Statements of Accounting Standards (SAS), which were largely outdated and inconsistent with international best practices. SAS lacked the depth and rigor required to address the complexities of modern financial reporting (Anetor & Osho, 2019; Oyedokun, & Balogun, 2022). Consequently, financial statements under SAS often failed to provide adequate information for decision-making.

With IFRS, Nigerian companies are required to present financial information in a way that better reflects their economic realities (Anetor & Osho, 2019). For example, IFRS emphasizes the use of fair value measurements, which provide more relevant information about an entity's financial position. Additionally, IFRS mandates extensive disclosure of accounting policies, estimates, risks, and uncertainties, which enhances transparency.

However, the actual impact of IFRS on financial reporting quality in Nigeria is still a subject of debate. While some studies report improvements in financial disclosures, others argue that the benefits of IFRS adoption are limited due to low compliance, inadequate enforcement, and insufficient capacity among preparers and auditors. As such, the realization of IFRS's full potential depends not only on adoption but also on effective implementation and oversight.

Theoretical Review

This study draws upon agency theory and stakeholders theory to explain the relationship between IFRS adoption and financial reporting quality. These theories help provide conceptual grounding for understanding how and why IFRS may influence reporting outcomes in various organizational and institutional contexts.

Agency Theory

Agency Theory posits a principal-agent relationship, where the principals (shareholders) delegate the running of the company to agents (managers) (Barth & Israeli, 2020). The core concern is the divergence of interests between the two parties. Agents may act in ways that benefit themselves rather than the principals, especially in environments where there is poor monitoring or lack of transparency. This conflict is exacerbated in firms where executive compensation is tied to financial performance, thus increasing the incentive for earnings manipulation or obfuscation of financial realities.

IFRS, with its emphasis on transparency, full disclosure, and faithful representation, is seen as a mechanism to mitigate agency problems (Barth & Israeli, 2020). By requiring detailed financial disclosures and standardized reporting, IFRS reduces the information asymmetry between agents and principals. As managers are required to disclose the economic substance of transactions and adhere to fair value accounting principles, their ability to mislead or conceal unfavorable information is significantly reduced. Thus, IFRS plays a critical role in aligning the interests of managers and shareholders and promoting accountability.

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder Theory expands the scope of accountability beyond just shareholders to include all stakeholders who are affected by the company's actions (Edeigba & Amenkhienan, 2019). These stakeholders include employees, creditors, suppliers, customers, government agencies, and the broader society. Under this theory, businesses are expected to balance the interests of all stakeholders and not focus solely on maximizing shareholder wealth.

In terms of financial reporting, this means providing information that is useful and accessible to a wide range of users. IFRS supports this broader accountability framework by providing a common language of financial reporting that is both comprehensive and comprehensible across jurisdictions. The theory supports the view that transparent financial reporting as mandated by IFRS can lead to increased stakeholder trust, improved corporate reputation, and long-term sustainability of firms. For a developing country like Nigeria, where investor confidence and public accountability are critical, Stakeholder Theory underscores the importance of adopting robust and inclusive reporting frameworks like IFRS.

Empirical Review

Oyedokun and Balogun (2022) looked at IFRS and financial reporting quality in Nigeria, using First Bank Plc as a case study. The research used a survey approach to experimentally evaluate the association between the variables IFRS and financial reporting quality in Nigerian banks. The study's participants are personnel (senior and junior) who work at several First Bank of Nigeria branches in Ibadan, Oyo state. The study's research instrument was a closed-ended self-structured questionnaire. The replies were coded, tabulated, and analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequency charts, and inferential statistics, such as regression analysis, to

assess the study's hypotheses. The findings revealed that First Bank Plc has a high level of IFRS compliance, as well as a substantial association between IFRS adoption and financial reporting quality. Based on the facts presented above, this study indicated that IFRS had an impact on the quality of financial reporting practices in Nigeria's banking sector. The study concluded that the financial reporting institutional framework should be strengthened by significantly empowering Nigeria's Financial Reporting Council. Also, the Financial Reporting Council's membership should be expanded to strengthen its influence beyond Nigeria's financial sector.

Oyedokun, Yunusa, and Adeyemo (2018) conducted an empirical study to determine the association between audit quality parameters and financial reporting quality in Nigerian publicly traded consumer products companies. The study used a correlational research methodology and selected 12 out of 17 quoted businesses in the industrial products sector using a purposive sampling technique to establish the sample size. The panel regression analysis using STATA revealed that audit firm size has a negative significant relationship, auditor tenure has a positive insignificant relationship, and audit fees have a negative insignificant relationship with the financial reporting quality of quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria. The study concluded that consumer goods companies should not rely on audit fees paid to auditors as a guarantee of qualitative financial reporting because audit fees have a negative and small impact on financial reporting quality. Consumer goods companies should not place an emphasis on auditor tenure and should carefully assess the size of audit firms before contracting them.

Odoemelam et al. (2019) examined the effect of IFRS adoption on the value relevance of accounting information in Nigeria. The study utilized a sample of 101 quoted firms covering the period 2006 to 2017, thereby capturing both pre-IFRS and post-IFRS adoption periods. Secondary data were sourced from annual reports, and the study employed the Ohlson price model using fixed effects panel regression techniques. The dependent variable was market price per share, while independent variables included earnings per share and book value per share. The findings revealed that IFRS adoption significantly improved the value relevance of earnings, although the impact on book value was not statistically significant. The study concluded that IFRS enhances the decision usefulness of financial information in Nigeria.

Nwaogwugwu (2020) investigated the impact of IFRS adoption on the financial performance and firm value of listed banks in Nigeria. The study focused on five selected banks over the period 2008–2015. Data were obtained from audited financial statements, and panel regression analysis (fixed effects model) was employed. Financial performance was proxied using Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Earnings per Share (EPS), while IFRS adoption was treated as a dummy variable. The results indicated that IFRS adoption had a positive but statistically insignificant effect on the performance indicators. The study concluded that

although IFRS adoption improves transparency, its effect on profitability may take time to materialize.

Ogunmakin et al. (2021) assessed the effect of IFRS adoption on the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study used a sample of 10 banks for the period 2006–2016. Secondary data were extracted from financial statements, and estimation techniques included pooled OLS, fixed effects, and random effects models. The dependent variables were ROA and ROE, while IFRS adoption served as the key explanatory variable. The findings showed that IFRS adoption had a statistically significant positive effect on bank performance. The study concluded that IFRS adoption improves comparability, transparency, and operational efficiency in the Nigerian banking sector.

Ajibade et al. (2022) explored the relationship between IFRS adoption, corporate governance, and financial reporting quality in Nigeria's development banks. The study employed panel data and regression analysis, focusing on governance variables such as board independence and audit committee effectiveness. Financial reporting quality was measured using faithful representation indicators. The study found that IFRS adoption significantly enhances financial reporting quality, particularly when supported by strong corporate governance mechanisms. It concluded that IFRS alone is insufficient without institutional support structures.

Ogala et al. (2023) examined the impact of IFRS adoption on earnings management among manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study compared pre-adoption (2008–2011) and post-adoption (2016–2020) periods. Data were analyzed using the Modified Jones Model to estimate discretionary accruals, alongside regression analysis. Earnings management served as the dependent variable, while IFRS adoption was the independent variable. The findings revealed that IFRS adoption significantly reduced earnings manipulation among firms. The study concluded that IFRS enhances the credibility and reliability of financial statements.

Uwadiachi and Ebiaghan (2026) analyzed the effect of IFRS adoption on financial performance in Nigeria using a longitudinal design. The study covered 18 listed banks over pre-adoption (2005–2011) and post-adoption (2018–2024) periods. Panel regression using fixed effects estimation was applied. The dependent variables included ROA and earnings quality, while IFRS adoption was treated as a policy variable. The results showed that IFRS adoption significantly improved financial performance and reporting quality over time. The study concluded that the long-term benefits of IFRS adoption outweigh initial implementation challenges.

Uwuigbe et al. (2017) investigated the effect of IFRS adoption on earnings predictability in Nigerian banks. The study used a sample of 11 listed banks and applied regression analysis to assess the relationship between IFRS adoption and future earnings predictability. The findings indicated that IFRS adoption reduced earnings predictability, suggesting increased volatility in reported earnings. The study argued that while IFRS enhances transparency, it may introduce variability due to fair value accounting practices.

Methodology

The study adopts a descriptive survey research design with a quantitative research approach. This design is appropriate because it facilitates the collection of first-hand data from respondents and allows for statistical analysis to determine the relationship between IFRS adoption and financial reporting quality. The study emphasizes numeric and objective assessment through structured instruments and statistical tools. The population comprises all quoted manufacturing companies on the NGX as of January 1, 2025, totaling 44 companies. These are firms officially recognized under the industrial and consumer goods sectors, among others. The choice of manufacturing companies is premised on their large asset base, structured accounting practices, and high compliance with reporting regulations. A sample of ten (10) manufacturing companies was purposively selected from the total population of 44. The sampling was based on the following criteria:

- i. Full compliance with IFRS reporting requirements.
- ii. Availability of complete audited financial statements from 2020 to 2024.
- iii. Representation across multiple sub-sectors.

List of Selected Manufacturing Companies:

S/N	Company Name	Sector	Location
1	Nestlé Nigeria Plc	Food & Beverages	Lagos State
2	Dangote Cement Plc	Cement/Industrial Goods	Lagos State
3	Unilever Nigeria Plc	Consumer Goods	Lagos State
4	Lafarge Africa Plc	Cement	Ogun State
5	Cadbury Nigeria Plc	Food & Beverages	Lagos State
6	BUA Cement Plc	Cement	Rivers State
7	Flour Mills of Nigeria Plc	Agro-Allied	Lagos State
8	Guinness Nigeria Plc	Alcoholic Beverages	Lagos State
9	PZ Cussons Nigeria Plc	Household Products	Lagos State
10	International Breweries Plc	Breweries	Ogun State

Secondary data was collected from Audited financial statements (2020–2024), Annual reports from the selected manufacturing companies, Publications from the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN), Market analysts’ reports and industry bulletins. Data collected was analyzed using both **descriptive** and **inferential** statistics. Descriptive Statistics made use of Frequencies, means, and standard deviations were computed to summarize responses while the **Inferential Statistics** involves **Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)** being the primary statistical tool for hypothesis testing. ANOVA was used to compare perceptions of financial reporting quality before and after IFRS adoption, analyze differences across sectors, company sizes, and

professional categories, test whether IFRS adoption significantly impacts elements like transparency, comparability, and faithful representation.

The general model to be applied is:

$$F = MS_{\text{between}} / MS_{\text{within}}$$

Where:

- i. **MS_{between}** = Mean Square Between Groups
- ii. **MS_{within}** = Mean Square Within Groups
- iii. A significant F-value will indicate differences in perceptions or outcomes.

Statistical analysis will be performed using SPSS version 25.0 or STATA, depending on available tools.

Result and Discussion of Findings

Descriptive Statistics

Inferential technique used to test for significant differences between groups, and descriptive statistics summarize central tendency and dispersion.

Table 1: ROA by YEAR (2020–2024)

YEAR	count	mean	std	min	25%	median	75%	max
2020	6	0.05883	0.11031	-0.102	0.009	0.0225	0.084	0.28
2021	6	0.07617	0.14145	-0.123	0.004	0.0350	0.127	0.34
2022	6	0.06992	0.10709	-0.050	0.012	0.0435	0.105	0.26
2023	6	0.05267	0.09844	-0.080	0.001	0.0230	0.075	0.19
2024	6	0.06517	0.09423	-0.034	0.011	0.0320	0.089	0.22

(Counts reflect number of ROA observations per year in the dataset.)

Interpretation: ROA means vary across years but remain in a similar band (approximately 0.05–0.08). Variability (std) is moderate and minimum values indicate some negative ROA observations in select years.

Table 2: ROA by SIZE category

Size	count	mean	std	min	25%	median	75%	max
Small	10	0.02120	0.04512	-0.102	-0.012	0.0100	0.041	0.085
Medium	10	0.04845	0.05478	-0.034	0.009	0.0380	0.071	0.14
Large	10	0.13780	0.06234	0.020	0.098	0.1340	0.162	0.34

Interpretation: Mean ROA increases with firm size category: Large firms exhibit substantially higher average ROA (0.1378) compared with Medium (0.0485) and Small (0.0212). Dispersion (std) is highest for Large firms but relative differences remain.

ANOVA Results

Table 3: One-way ANOVA — ROA by YEAR

Source	DF	F	p-value
Between Groups	4	0.5854	0.804339
Within Groups	26		
Total	30		

Interpretation: The ANOVA test indicates no statistically significant differences in mean ROA across years 2020–2024 ($F(4,26) = 0.5854, p = 0.8043$). Thus, we fail to reject the null hypothesis that mean ROA is equal across the five years.

Table 4: One-way ANOVA — ROA by SIZE category

Source	DF	F	p-value
Between Groups	2	13.1752	0.000013
Within Groups	27		
Total	29		

Interpretation: The ANOVA indicates highly significant differences in mean ROA between SIZE groups ($F(2,27) = 13.1752, p < 0.001$). Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis of equal mean ROA across size categories; post-hoc tests are recommended to identify which pairs differ.

Post-hoc Recommendation and Effect Size

Because the SIZE-based ANOVA is significant, a **Tukey HSD** post-hoc test is recommended to pinpoint specific group differences (e.g., Large vs Medium, Large vs Small, Medium vs Small). Preliminary descriptive results suggest the significant differences are driven by Large firms having higher ROA than Medium and Small firms. Calculating **eta-squared** or **omega-squared** will provide effect-size measures for the between-group variance explained by SIZE.

Linking Results to Research Objectives and Hypotheses

Objective: To determine whether IFRS adoption has influenced financial reporting quality (proxied here by ROA) across time and firm characteristics.

Finding (YEAR): No evidence that mean ROA changed significantly across 2020–2024 (ANOVA not significant). This suggests that, at least for ROA, there is no clear temporal change within this span that can be associated with progressive IFRS effects.

Finding (SIZE): Strong evidence that firm size is associated with ROA differences; larger firms show higher ROA, which could reflect better IFRS implementation, stronger governance, higher audit quality, or economies of scale.

Hypotheses:

H₀ (No difference in ROA by year): **Not rejected.**

H₀ (No difference in ROA by size): **Rejected** — size significantly influences ROA.

Discussion of Findings

The purpose of this study was to examine the impact of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) adoption on financial reporting quality in Nigerian quoted manufacturing companies between 2020 and 2024. Return on Assets (ROA) was employed as a proxy indicator for financial reporting quality because it reflects both profitability and management efficiency, which are critical signals of transparent and reliable reporting. Descriptive statistics and ANOVA tests were applied to explore variations across time (2020–2024) and across firm size categories (Small, Medium, Large).

Findings in Relation to Years (2020–2024)

The descriptive results showed only modest year-to-year variation in ROA, with mean values ranging from 0.0527 in 2023 to 0.0762 in 2021. The ANOVA results ($F(4,26) = 0.5854$, $p = 0.8043$) revealed no statistically significant differences in ROA across the years under review. This suggests that the adoption of IFRS and its continuous application during 2020–2024 did not result in clear, measurable improvements in profitability or transparency when viewed solely through ROA.

This finding is consistent with some previous Nigerian studies (e.g., empirical reviews by Okafor, 2020; Adeyemi & Fagbemi, 2021) which observed that the benefits of IFRS adoption are often undermined by weak enforcement, low compliance, and technical implementation gaps. From the theoretical standpoint, the result challenges the **Agency Theory** expectation that higher transparency through IFRS should constrain managerial opportunism and improve performance. Similarly, the **Signaling Theory** proposition that IFRS adoption would signal credibility and improve investor confidence does not strongly materialize here, at least not in short-term profitability.

Findings in Relation to Firm Size

A stronger pattern emerged when ROA was analyzed across firm sizes. Large firms demonstrated substantially higher mean ROA (0.1378) compared to medium (0.0485) and

small (0.0212) firms. The ANOVA test confirmed these differences as statistically significant ($F(2,27) = 13.1752, p < 0.001$). This indicates that firm size significantly affects financial performance and, by implication, financial reporting quality.

This finding aligns with Institutional Theory and Legitimacy Theory, which suggest that larger firms, facing more scrutiny from regulators, auditors, and international investors, are more motivated to comply with IFRS rigorously to maintain legitimacy and global competitiveness. Larger firms also tend to have more resources and technical expertise to implement complex IFRS requirements effectively, reducing information asymmetry and enhancing reporting quality. This supports the Information Asymmetry Theory view that transparency improves more in settings where compliance is stronger and resources are available.

Implications for Stakeholders

The findings imply that IFRS adoption in Nigeria has not automatically translated into improved reporting quality across all companies or over time. Instead, benefits appear unevenly distributed, favoring larger firms that possess the technical and financial capacity to implement IFRS more effectively. This reinforces concerns highlighted in the Statement of Problem that enforcement gaps and limited technical capacity hinder full realization of IFRS benefits.

For regulators such as the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) and the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX), the results emphasize the need for stronger enforcement mechanisms and capacity-building initiatives targeted at smaller and medium-sized firms. For investors, the findings signal caution in interpreting financial reports of smaller firms, as they may be less reflective of true economic reality due to weaker IFRS compliance.

Link back to research hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in financial reporting quality (proxied by ROA) across years (2020–2024).

Decision: Not rejected. The ANOVA indicated no significant yearly differences.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in financial reporting quality across firm size categories.

Decision: Rejected. Significant differences were found, with larger firms exhibiting higher ROA.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The findings of this study lead to the conclusion that the adoption of IFRS has not resulted in significant year-to-year improvements in financial reporting quality in Nigerian quoted manufacturing firms between 2020 and 2024. Although the adoption of IFRS has standardized reporting practices, the persistence of weak institutional capacity, inadequate enforcement, and limited technical expertise has restricted its effectiveness in producing measurable improvements in reporting quality. It is further concluded that larger firms benefit more from

IFRS adoption because they possess the resources, skilled personnel, and governance structures required to comply with complex international standards, whereas smaller firms continue to face significant difficulties in compliance. The study therefore concludes that IFRS adoption is not a stand-alone solution to improving financial reporting quality but must be supported by strong regulatory enforcement, adequate training, and institutional strengthening if it is to achieve its intended objectives in Nigeria.

This study therefore recommended that regulatory authorities such as the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria and the Nigerian Exchange Group should intensify their efforts to ensure strict compliance with IFRS requirements across all quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. It also recommends that accountants, auditors, and financial managers should be regularly trained through workshops and capacity-building programs to enhance their technical expertise in IFRS application. Furthermore, the study recommends that smaller firms should be supported with tax reliefs, subsidies, or technical assistance programs that will reduce the financial burden of IFRS compliance and enable them to benefit more from its adoption. It also recommends that audit firms should continue to strengthen their capacity to deliver high-quality audits that will safeguard against misreporting and enhance the reliability of financial statements. Another recommendation is that boards of directors in manufacturing firms should prioritize financial transparency and accountability through sound corporate governance practices that align with IFRS principles. Finally, the study recommends that firms should integrate modern accounting technologies and software that are IFRS-compliant in order to reduce reporting errors, improve efficiency, and ensure timely presentation of financial statements.

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